

Monitoring of Dimensional Stability of CFRP Mirrors for Space Telescopes by Using Embedded FBG Sensors

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SUMMARY

The dimensional stability of CFRP mirrors for space telescopes was studied. Surface accuracy was improved to 70 nm RMS by a replica technique. Moisture expansion, which has caused an unpredictable error on orbit, was monitored by using embedded FBG sensors under constant temperature and moisture conditions.

Keywords: CFRP, Space Telescope, Mirror, Thermal Expansion, Moisture Expansion, Dimensional Stability, FBG Sensor, Optical Fiber, Surface Accuracy

INTRODUCTION

Space telescopes for Earth observation will require data of increasingly high quality. The resolution of Earth observation has reached several tens of cm. Because resolution is proportional to the diameter of mirrors, larger and larger mirrors are required. Space astronomy telescopes also require increasingly high resolution and large mirrors. The James Webb Space Telescope has been already advanced to the developing phases and the deployable main mirror of 6 m in diameter is being manufactured [1]. Although the structure of telescopes is based mainly on system design, the selection of material is a key issue on points of high dimensional accuracy and stability, especially with regard to weight. Carbon fiber-reinforced composite (CFRP) has a high stiffness-to-weight ratio and can be designed to have nearly zero thermal expansion [2]. That makes CFRP one of the most promising materials for optical mirrors of space telescopes.

Fig. 1 Surface precision of space telescope mirrors as a function of aperture diameters

Fig. 1 shows the precision of the mirrors as a function of telescope aperture size. Three typical materials are compared, namely CFRP, low thermal expansion glass, and SiC. Deformation due to the weight of the mirrors is proportional to the square of the diameter. Dimensional stability against on-orbit loads is determined by the eigenvalues of the structures. Thermal stability on orbit depends on linear thermal expansion and is proportional to the diameter. SiC, which has the highest specific modulus, is the best material for large mirrors, whereas low thermal expansion glass is best for the small but most precise mirrors. CFRP has superior properties as regards the combination of high specific modulus and low thermal expansion for middle-size mirrors.

CFRP has additional advantages in that its density is lower than the other materials and thin-wall structures are easy to construct. This is essential for lightweight structures. Cost effective manufacturing of large-scale telescopes with CFRP mirrors is of advantage over that of telescopes with mirrors made of the other two materials. Disregarding these advantages, CFRP mirrors have not been manufactured except for the developing models [3]. The reason is that surface accuracy of CFRP mirrors has not satisfied the accuracy required for space telescopes of visible or near-infrared light to several tenths of a wavelength. The following issues must be resolved in order to achieve a stable wave front of required properties:

1. achieve an appropriate and durable surface for optical polishing to attain the required surface precision,
2. demonstrate dimensional stability against the space environment,
3. verify long-term dimensional stability.

Differences in physical and mechanical properties between fibers and matrix make it difficult to polish the CFRP mirror surface to the required nm-scale precision for near-infrared or visible-light telescopes. This often causes undulation of the CFRP surface, or what is called print-through. The polymer matrix may be degraded by the space environment. Inherent thermal stresses may cause unpredictable long-term dimensional changes due to creep of the polymer matrix.

In this paper, we discuss the adequacy of CFRP mirrors. Studies on CFRP deformation in the sub-micron meter scale have been very few and we have systematically investigated the temperature dependence of CFRP distortion [4]. Moisture absorption and desorption causes a relatively large dimensional change in CFRP structures [5], and the difficulty of measuring the moisture absorption quantity of actual components causes unpredictable surface errors on orbit. FBG sensors embedded in CFRP are demonstrated as a useful tool for monitoring deformation due to moisture expansion.

CFRP MIRRORS

Composition of CFRP Mirrors

Fig.2 shows a $\phi 300$ diameter mirror sample of a sandwich structure. The surface layer was composed of CFRP with high elastic pitch-based carbon fiber and cyanate ester resin matrix. The honeycomb core was made of the same material. A high elastic carbon fiber, YSH50-A, was chosen to achieve a nearly zero thermal expansion and the fiber volume fraction was controlled in the curing process by using bleeder cloths. Cyanate ester resin was chosen because its moisture absorption is much lower than that

of epoxy. Sandwich panels were composed of quasi-isotropic CFRP skins 1.76 mm in thickness and CFRP honeycomb cores 40 mm in thickness. The thickness of the skins was determined to be as small as possible but without print-through of the cores on the mirror surface. 16 plies of unidirectional prepreg were symmetrically laminated and then cured in an autoclave. The density was 1680 kg/m³. The honeycomb cores were made of single layer cloth. The areal density of the sandwich panels was 9 kg/m².

Fig.2 Photographs of mirrors of CFRP/CFRP honeycomb-core sandwich panels

Dimensional Accuracy of the CFRP Mirrors

The dimensional accuracy of the mirrors was measured by using a non-contact laser surface profiler. Table 1 shows the dimensional accuracy of a CFRP mirror which was cured by means of an Invar tool. The radius of curvature tended to be smaller than that of the tool and the accuracy was slightly degraded. The surface configuration difference between the tool and CFRP suggested that the convex was evenly deepened (Fig.3).

Table 1 Dimensional Accuracy of the CFRP Mirrors

	Radius (mm)	Accuracy (μm)	Surface Roughness (μm)	
Tool	1002.415	3.53	-	-
CFRP Mirror	999.140	6.00	3.79 PV*	0.47 RMS*

*PV: Peak to Valley, RMS: Root Mean Square

Fig.3 Dimensional change of the mirror from the tool, perpendicular to the surface

In the surface roughness, two kinds of undulations were discerned (Fig.4). One was a 0.1 mm pitch and a 3 μm PV roughness, which seemed to come from a machining bite trace. The other was a 7 μm pitch and a 0.8 μm PV roughness, which was related to fiber print-through. The fiber print-through patterns were in the same direction as the fiber orientation of the utmost layer and also as the second and third layers.

(a) Surface roughness of the mirror (b) Magnified section

Fig4. Surface roughness of the mirror cured using an Invar tool

Thermal Expansion

The coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) and the coefficient of moisture expansion (CME) are shown in Table 2 and Fig.4, respectively. The CTE of the sandwich panels was measured by means of an optical interferometer. The CTE of the sandwich panels was larger than that of the CFRP plates. This difference comes from the positive CTE of the adhesive layers and honeycomb cores. The results of CTE measurements suggested that the thermal expansion of CFRP could be controlled within $\pm 1 \times 10^{-7} / \text{K}$.

Table 2 CTE and CME

	CTE ($10^{-7}/\text{K}$) 20~80°C	CME ($10^{-4}/\%$)
CFRP Plate	-1.3 ± 0.5	1.9
Sandwich Panel	1.0 ± 0.5	-

Fig.5 An example of CTE measurement

Surface Finishing

The as-cured surface of the CFRP had fiber print-through patterns and did not satisfy the surface roughness requirement for space telescope mirrors as shown in Fig.4. An effort to improve surface roughness was made by using a replica technique. Resin of low viscosity was applied on a glass tool with highly smooth surface and a $\lambda/10$ accuracy to form a very thin layer less than a few tens of μm . Then CFRP skin was placed on the resin film. After it was cured, the resin layer of the smooth surface was attached to the skin and removed from the tool. Fig.6 shows the improvement in surface roughness by the replica technique. Fig. 6(a) is the mirror surface shown in Fig. 4. Fig. 6(b) is a mirror which was cured by using a low thermal expansion glass tool with a surface accuracy of $\lambda/10$. Tool patterns were removed but fiber print-through still remained, though surface roughness was improved to $0.8 \mu\text{m PV}$. Fig. 6(c) shows the replicated surface whose roughness was improved to $0.2 \mu\text{m PV}$ and $0.07 \mu\text{m RMS}$. The replicated sample had no print-through patterns of fibers. However, the edge line of a fluorescent light in the photographs was not clear enough and seemed to have a small undulation. Our investigation of replica techniques will be continued to get a nm-scale smooth surface.

Fig. 6 Surface roughness improvement

MOISTURE EXPANSION

It is well known that CFRP absorbs moisture and expands. Saturated water contents at room temperature were approximately 0.3% in CFRP with cyanate matrix. On the other hand, epoxy matrix CFRP absorbed moisture of more than 1%. Fig.7 shows the change in specimen weight measured with an electronic precision balance.

Fig.7 Moisture absorption of CFRP plates

FBG sensors embedded in CFRP were demonstrated to be a useful tool for measuring the temperature or strain of CFRP. The sensitivity of FBG sensors was 0.5 ppm, which is equivalent to a temperature of 0.05 K and a strain of 0.3 μ . The accuracy of the FBG measurement was estimated to be 0.1K and 2 μ strain, respectively [6]. Fig.8 (a) shows the peak wavelengths of FBG reflected light when CFRP specimens were aged at 40 °C and 90% RH (Relative Humidity). The peak spectra of the reflected light wave did not change and only peak wavelengths shifted. This means that CFRP specimens were uniformly deformed in the plane, and peak shifts represented the elongation of CFRP under the conditions of this experiment. Fig.8 (b) is re-plotted as elongation vs. square root of time. The elongation seemed proportional to the square root of time from 3 to 8 $\sqrt{\text{hr}}$ except at the initial stage where temperature was not even and at the final stage where absorption reached near saturation. The square root law suggested that water absorption was controlled by the diffusion rate of water in CFRP and moisture expansion was proportional to the water absorbed contents. The elongation saturated near 110 hr. CME was calculated based on the elongation measured by FBG and the weight change of specimens, which were treated under the same conditions without embedded FBG sensors. CME was $1.9 \times 10^{-4}/\%$. Assuming that CFRP mirrors would absorb 0.1% moisture on the ground and then be launched, CFRP might extend to 2×10^{-5} strains and then shrink on orbit. This dimensional change might be equivalent to a 100 K temperature change.

(a) Wave length change of FBG peak

(b) Elongation vs. square root of time

Fig.8 Moisture expansion of CFRP in 40°C and 90% RH

Fig.9 shows moisture expansion of the sandwich panel at 60°C and at 90% RH. The maximum elongation was almost equal to the value calculated by using the saturated water absorption quantity in Fig.7 and a CME of $1.9 \times 10^{-4}/\%$.

Fig.9 Moisture expansion of CFRP/CFRP honeycomb sandwich panel

Fig.10 shows the shrinkage of water-saturated CFRP when the specimens were heated in vacuum. A duration of 150 min was required before saturation of the shrinkage at 120°C in vacuum. The time for saturation depended on the thickness of specimens. The calculated CME based on FBG elongation and weight loss was $2.2 \times 10^{-4}/\%$ in this case. This figure suggested that CFRP structures would gradually distort in space. Given that it is difficult to measure water absorption content in real CFRP components on the ground, this change would degrade the precision of satellite structures, as it would be an unknown factor in the error budget. These results demonstrated that FBG sensors were a useful tool for monitoring the dimensional change of CFRP space optical components.

Fig.10 Dimensional change of CFRP in vacuum by water dissipation

CONCLUSION

The adequacy of CFRP as a mirror material for space telescopes was discussed. CTE was designed to be $1 \times 10^{-7}/K$ for CFRP/CFRP honeycomb core sandwich panels. Fiber print-through patterns remained on the as-cured CFRP surface. The surface accuracy did not satisfy the nm level requirements for visible or near-infrared telescopes. Replica

techniques have the potential to improve surface roughness. Surface finishing techniques to get enough smooth surfaces must be investigated extensively.

Moisture Expansion was considered as one of the major causes of unpredictable dimensional errors on orbit. Elongations of CFRP were monitored by means of embedded FBG sensors under constant temperature and moisture conditions. Moisture expansion was proportional to the square root of time and CME was $1.9 \times 10^{-4}/K$. The accuracy of the sensors was estimated to be 0.1 K in temperature and 2×10^{-6} in strain. FBG sensors embedded in CFRP were a useful tool for monitoring moisture expansion.

The potential of CFRP seemed to be very promising. In this study, CTE and CME were discussed as in-plane elongation. A change in the surface accuracy of mirrors may occur in a direction perpendicular to the surfaces. Coupling mechanisms of out-of-plane strains with in-plane strains must be investigated.

References

1. NASA Homepage, www.jwst.nasa.gov
2. Ozaki T., Naito K., Mikami I., Yamauchi H., "High precision composite pipes for SOLAR-B optical structures", *Acta Astronautica*, Vol.48, pp.321-329, 2001
3. Connell S.J., Abusafieh A., "Light space mirrors from carbon fiber composites", *SAMPE Journal*, Vol.38, No.4, pp.46, 2002
4. Arao Y., Koyanagi J., Utsunomiya S., Kawada H., "Time dependent out-of-plane deformation of UD-CFRP in humid environment", *Composite Science and Technology*, (in press)
5. Arao Y., Koyanagi J., Hatta H., Kawada H., "Dimensional change of CFRP taking account of moisture concentration", *Journal of Japan Society for Composite Materials*, Vol.34, No.3, (2008) (in Japanese)
6. Utsunomiya S., Shimizu R., "Moisture expansion monitoring of CFRP using FBG sensors", *Proceeding of 33th Japanese Composite Materials Symposium*, (2008.10) (in Japanese)